

Microwave-assisted volatile oil extraction and composition of seeds of *Cassia tora* (L.)

Noreen Azeem[‡], Zeeshan Ahmad[‡], Azeem Intisar^{1*}, Adnan Mujahid[€], Tajamal Hussain^λ, Ahsan Sharif^º, Ejaz Ahmed[€], Anza Zafar[€]

Institute of Chemistry, University of the Punjab, Lahore-54590, Pakistan.

To cite this article:

Noreen Azeem, Zeeshan Ahmad, Azeem Intisar, Adnan Mujahid, Tajamal Hussain, Ahsan Sharif, Ejaz Ahmed, Anza Zafar, “Microwave-assisted volatile oil extraction and composition of seeds of *Cassia tora* (L.)”, Parana Journal of Science and Education, Vol. 4, No. 9, 2018, pp. 8-12.

Received: December 13, 2018; **Accepted:** December 26, 2018; **Published:** December 27, 2018.

Abstract

In this study, volatile oil of seeds of *Cassia tora* (L.) was extracted with microwave-assisted extraction methodology followed by Gas chromatography mass spectrometric analysis that led to the identification of 35 constituents representing a total of 73.35% of the total oil composition. Results revealed that the plant was rich in fatty acids where major ingredients were: linoleic acid (26.71%), palmitic acid (25.28%), indole (2.56%) and oleamide (2.08%). Moreover, many oil constituents were well-known aroma imparting compounds with bioactive properties.

Keywords: *Cassia tora* Linn., Seeds, Volatile oils, Linoleic acid, Palmitic acid.

[‡]E-mail: noreenazeem15@gmail.com

[‡]E-mail: zeeshanchemist@yahoo.com

^{1*}E-mail: azeemintisar.chem@pu.edu.pk (Corresponding author)

[€]E-mail: adnanmujahid.chem@pu.edu.pk

^λE-mail: tajamalhussain.chem@pu.edu.pk

^ºE-mail: chahsansharif@yahoo.com

[€]E-mail: dr.ejaz.ahmed@gmail.com

[€]E-mail: anzazafarullah@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Cassia tora Linn. belongs to 'Fabaceae' family [1, 2] has many local names as Sickie senna [3] (English), Chakvad (Hindi), Sanamakki (Urdu). It is a shrub [4] that is found in Asian countries [5] such as India, Sri Lanka [6], West China [7] and Pakistan [8]. Among all parts, its seeds are the most beneficial for food [9] as a source of dietary fibers [10], proteins [11], minerals and starch [12, 13]. Leaves and seeds are applied for treatment of various disorders [14] such as bronchitis, colic, joint pain [15], lowering of cholesterol level, antiasthenic disease, leprosy [16], reduction in blood pressure and sciatica [17, 18]. Furthermore, plant exhibits numerous pharmacological activities including antihypertensive, anti-microbial [2], antifungal, anti-tumor [4], hypolipidemic [19], spasmolytic, antibacterial [7], anti-inflammatory [6] and anti-mutagenic properties [20]. Phytochemistry of the plant demonstrated that plant contains naturally occurring polyphenols, fatty acids [21], esters, indols [22, 23], amino acids [21], alcohols, sterols [24] and essential oils [25].

The main purpose of this study was to determine the volatile oil composition of seeds of *Cassia tora* (L.) from Pakistan.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Plant material and oil extraction

Dried seeds of *Cassia tora* were purchased from Sheikhpura, Pakistan and 100 grams of ground material was subjected to microwave-assisted hydro distillation for 2 hours and oil was collected in n-hexane. Oil was stored in a refrigerator at low temperature (-10°C) before analysis.

2.2 Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry

Separation of oil constituents was carried out at Agilent machine on a non-polar DB-5 MS column with dimensions (30 m × 0.25 mm ID × 0.25 µm film thickness). One (1) µL injection volume was introduced. Carrier gas (helium) at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Temperature ramp was employed as follows: starting temperature

was 50°C that was held for 3 min and mass spectrometer signal was turned off till that time then the temperature was raised at a rate of 15°C/min to 295°C. The mass detector was in EI mode with following conditions: temperatures of ion source, transfer line and detector were 230°C, 250°C and 280°C, respectively where mass range (m/z) of 35~500 was selected. 2200V (multi-channel plate voltage) and 70eV (ionizing voltage) were employed.

3. Results and Discussion

Pale yellow colored oil from seeds of *Cassia tora* Linn. was extracted and a yield of 0.16% was obtained. A total of 35 constituents that accounted for 73.35% of total volatile oils, were identified by matching their mass spectra with NIST-2011 library. Furthermore, retention indices were calculated by running standard alkanes (C8-C30) by comparing with the standard data given in literature [26]. The most abundant compounds were: linoleic acid (26.71%), palmitic acid (25.28%), indole (2.56%) and oleamide (2.08%). Constituents were arranged in the order of their increasing retention times and retention indices as shown in Table (1) whereas Table (2) showed the classification of volatile oil constituents.

As compared to the previous report on seed oil extracted with supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) [25], along with notable similarities few considerable differences were also observed. Major components obtained from SFE were linoleic acid (26.74%), oleic acid (24.15%) and palmitic acid (13.99%) whereas in current study with MAE linoleic acid (26.71%), palmitic acid (25.28%) and indole (2.56%) were obtained where similarity regarding the two out of 3 major constituents was obvious, however, oleic acid was found to be much lower in its abundance in MAE and indole (2.56%) was only observed in MAE.

This difference in chemical composition may have been the reason of various factors such as the oil extraction methodology and growing origin of plant with different soil and environmental conditions [27, 28].

Table 1: Volatile chemical compounds of *Cassia tora* (L.) seeds

No.	Retention time (min)	Retention indices RI _{Lit}	Retention indices RI _{Cal}	Names of identified constituents	Abundance (%)
1.	3.135	746	-	Disulfide, dimethyl	0.48
2.	4.199	828	-	1H-Pyrrole, 1-ethyl-	0.42
3.	4.317	830	-	Pyrazine, methyl-	0.34
4.	4.520	835	833	Furfural	t
5.	5.093	867	869	1H-Pyrrole, 2,5-dimethyl-	0.40
6.	5.413	889	889	2-Heptanone	0.47
7.	5.729	906	909	Pyrazine, 2,6-dimethyl-	0.69
8.	6.480	961	961	Benzaldehyde	0.30
9.	6.520	963	964	5-methyl-2-furfural	t
10.	6.930	991	992	Furfuryl acetate	0.51
11.	6.986	997	996	Pyrazine, 2-ethyl-6-methyl-	0.46
12.	7.029	998	999	Furan, 2-[(methylthio)methyl]-	0.54
13.	8.018	1082	1079	Pyrazine, 3-ethyl-2,5-dimethyl	0.65
14.	8.746	1143	1142	Benzyl nitrile	1.42
15.	9.160	1184	1180	Furan, 2-(2-furanylmethyl)-5-methyl-	0.54
16.	9.211	1185	1185	1H-Pyrrole, 1-(2-furanylmethyl)-	1.34
17.	9.821	1244	1244	Benzene propanenitrile	1.26
18.	10.380	1295	1301	Indole	2.56
19.	10.540	1317	1318	p-Vinylguaiaicol	t
20.	11.250	-	1395	6-Methylindole	1.15
21.	14.140	1762	1760	Myristic acid	0.32
22.	14.390	1800	1797	Octadecane	t
23.	14.590	1812	1816	Isopropyl myristate	0.28
24.	14.830	1857	1854	Pentadecanoic acid	t
25.	14.980	1900	1895	Nonadecane	0.51
26.	15.270	1916	1919	Palmitic acid, methyl ester	0.88
27.	15.440	1944	1946	Palmitoleic acid	t
28.	15.650	1972	1976	Palmitic acid	25.28
29.	16.380	2092	2090	Linoleic acid, methyl ester	0.65
30.	16.410	2095	2095	Oleic acid, methyl ester	t
31.	16.790	2159	2158	Linoleic acid	26.71

32.	16.840	2161	2166	Oleic acid	t
33.	16.910	2180	2178	Stearic acid	1.90
34.	17.990	2375	2365	Oleamide	2.08
35.	18.060	-	2380	Chrysophanol	1.21

Total identified percentage of volatile oil = 73.35%; t = trace; RI_{Cal} = Calculated RI; RI_{Lit} = RI from literature.

Table 2: Classification of oils of *Cassia tora* (L.)

Classes of volatile constituents	Serial number of compounds	(%)
Aldehydes	4, 8, 9	0.30
Fatty acids	21, 24, 27, 28, 31, 32, 33	54.21
Hydrocarbons	22, 25	0.51
Esters	10, 23, 26, 29, 30	2.32
Pyrroles	2, 5, 16	2.16
Pyrazines	3, 7, 11, 13	2.14
Others	1, 6, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 34, 35	11.71

Overall classification of SFE and MAE extracted oil compositions demonstrated that fatty acids were the predominant classes in both studies and percentages were 75.90% and 54.21%, respectively that showed remarkable similarity. Moreover, common fatty acids were pentadecanoic acid, linoleic acid, oleic acid and stearic acid. Various other constituents such as fatty acids esters, chrysophanol etc., were common among the oils. Most of these fatty acids and few other constituents are well-known active ingredients.

4. Conclusion

The oil from the seeds of *Cassia tora* (L.) consisted of 35 constituents that were separated and identified successfully where the most abundant components were linoleic acid (26.71%), palmitic acid (25.28%), indole (2.56%) and oleamide (2.08%) where fatty

acids were found to be the most dominating class of compounds.

Acknowledgement

Authors pay thanks to the University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan for providing financial aid for the completion of this study.

References

- [1] Y. -M. Kim et al., "Anthraquinones isolated from *Cassia tora* (Leguminosae) seed show an antifungal property against phytopathogenic fungi", *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, **2004**. 52(20): p. 6096-6100.
- [2] P. K. Mukherjee et al., "Antifungal activities of the leaf extract of *Cassia tora* Linn. (Fam. Leguminosae)", *Phytotherapy Research*, **1996**. 10(6): p. 521-522.
- [3] S. K. Shukla et al., "The probable medicinal usage of *Cassia tora*: an overview". *Online journal of biological sciences*, **2013**. 13(1): p. 13.
- [4] J. S. Choi et al., "In vitro antimutagenic effects of anthraquinone aglycones and naphthopyrone glycosides from *Cassia tora*", *Planta medica*, **1997**. 63(01): p. 11-14.
- [5] J. F. Ma, S. J. Zheng H. Matsumoto, "Specific secretion of citric acid induced by Al stress in *Cassia tora* L", *Plant and cell physiology*, **1997**. 38(9): p. 1019-1025.
- [6] T. K. Maity et al., "Studies on antiinflammatory effect of *Cassia tora* leaf extract (fam. Leguminosae)", *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological*

and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives, **1998**. 12(3): p. 221-223.

[7] U. K. Patil, S. Saraf, V. Dixit, "Hypolipidemic activity of seeds of Cassia tora Linn", *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, **2004**. 90(2-3): p. 249-252.

[8] Y. -S. Wang, Z. -M. Yang, "Nitric oxide reduces aluminum toxicity by preventing oxidative stress in the roots of Cassia tora L.", *Plant and cell physiology*, **2005**. 46(12): p. 1915-1923.

[9] Y. P. Lee, I. B. Puddey, J. M. Hodgson, "Protein, fibre and blood pressure: potential benefit of legumes", *Clinical and experimental pharmacology & physiology*, **2008**. 35(4): p. 473-476.

[10] M. J. Messina, "Legumes and soybeans: overview of their nutritional profiles and health effects", *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, **1999**. 70(3): p. 439s-450s.

[11] Z. Madar, A. H. Stark, "New legume sources as therapeutic agents", *British Journal of Nutrition*, **2002**. 88(S3): p. 287-292.

[12] D. Jezierny, R. Mosenthin, E. Bauer, "The use of grain legumes as a protein source in pig nutrition: A review", *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, **2010**. 157(3-4): p. 111-128.

[13] W. Hargrove, "Winter Legumes as a Nitrogen Source for No-Till Grain Sorghum 1", *Agronomy Journal*, **1986**. 78(1): p. 70-74.

[14] A. Chatterjee, S. C. Pakrashi, "The treatise on Indian medicinal plants", vol. 1. New Delhi: Publications and Information Directorate, CSIR 172p.-illus., col. illus. ISBN 8172360118 En Icones. Includes authentic Sanskrit slokas in both Devnagri and Roman scripts, *Plant records*. Geog, **1991**. 6.

[15] T. Nikaido et al., "Inhibitors of adenosine 3', 5'-cyclic monophosphate phosphodiesterase in Cassia seed", *Chemical and pharmaceutical bulletin*, **1984**. 32(8): p. 3075-3078.

[16] S. K. Jain, "Dictionary of Indian folk medicine and ethnobotany", **1991**: *Deep publications*.

[17] L. Kapoor, "Handbook of Ayurvedic medicinal plants: Herbal reference library", **2017**. *Routledge*.

[18] K. Hemadri, S. S. Rao, "Jaundice: tribal medicine", *Ancient science of life*, **1984**. 3(4): p. 209.

[19] G. -C. Yen, H. -W. Chen, P. -D. Duh, "Extraction and identification of an antioxidative component from Jue Ming Zi (Cassia tora L.)", *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, **1998**. 46(3): p. 820-824.

[20] C. -H. Wu, G. -C. Yen, "Antigenotoxic properties of Cassia tea (Cassia tora L.): Mechanism of action and the influence of roasting process", *Life sciences*, **2004**. 76(1): p. 85-101.

[21] M. Choudhary, Y. Gulia, "Cassia tora: Its chemistry, medicinal uses and pharmacology", *Pharmacologyonline*, **2011**. 3(1): p. 78-96.

[22] J. A. Generali, D. J. Cada, "Ondansetron: Postanesthetic Shivering", *Hospital Pharmacy*, **2009**. 44(8): p. 670-671.

[23] R. Horton, "Lotronex and the FDA: a fatal erosion of integrity", *The Lancet*, **2001**. 357(9268): p. 1544-1545.

[24] A. Ingle et al., "Cassia tora: phytochemical and pharmacological activity. International Imperial", *Journal of Pharmacognosy & Natural Products*, **2012**. 2(1): p. 14-23.

[25] Y. Zhang et al., "Chemical components and antioxidant activity of the volatile oil from Cassia tora L. seed prepared by supercritical fluid extraction", *Journal of food lipids*, **2007**. 14(4): p. 411-423.

[26] NIST Standard Reference Database Number 69. URL: <https://webbook.nist.gov/chemistry/> .

[27] A. Intisar et al., "Anticancer constituents and cytotoxic activity of methanol-water extract of Polygonum bistorta L.", *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, **2013**. 10(1): p. 53-59.

[28] E. E. Stashenko, B. E. Jaramillo, J. R. Martínez, "Comparison of different extraction methods for the analysis of volatile secondary metabolites of Lippia alba (Mill.) NE Brown, grown in Colombia, and evaluation of its in vitro antioxidant activity", *Journal of Chromatography A*, **2004**. 1025(1): p. 93-103.